

An optimized probabilistic forecasting approach for hybridized wind power plants

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Abstract

Accurate forecasts are essential for effectively integrating variable renewable power plants into power systems and electricity markets. Since hybrid power plants are a new area of research, several key challenges need to be addressed. This work presents a probabilistic power forecast approach to hybridised wind power plants with solar power. The forecasting methodology uses a sequential forward feature selection algorithm, employing distinct objective functions and an artificial neural network approach. The probabilistic power forecasts are obtained using a quantile spline regression technique. The approach supports the identification of the i) optimal quantile and ii) the exogenous features (e.g., meteorological input features from numerical weather prediction – NWP models) to increase the profitability of the hybrid power plants in an electricity market environment. As expected, hybridization increases the remuneration of the producer compared to existing wind plants, regardless of complementarity levels. However, the increase in remuneration is superior in the case study with the highest generation complementarity. The use of quantiles to calibrate the forecast approach proves to be crucial for increasing the remuneration compared to the traditional deterministic approach based on the power forecast expected value.

1 Introduction

One of the key challenges in the power system sector relies on integrating variable renewable energy sources (vRES), particularly wind and solar photovoltaic (PV) power, in a cost-effective sustainable manner. Currently, to support the transmission system operators (TSOs) in constantly ensuring a balance between electricity production and consumption accurate vRES and consumption forecasts are crucial [1]. These forecasts minimize the need for costly balancing measures in reserve markets [2]. As nearly 100% power systems become a reality, the importance of accurate forecasting systems will be even more noticeable [3].

Forecasts also play a crucial role in electricity markets. Market participants rely on forecast systems to establish their bidding strategies for the electricity markets. In existing market structures, deviations from scheduled bids by power producers result in penalties and substantial profit reductions. For instance, the day-ahead markets (DAM), typically require forecasts with a time horizon of 12 to 36 hours, which can lead to significant power forecast errors [4]. For this time horizon, forecast methods based on numerical weather prediction (NWP) models outperform other techniques, such as autoregressive models, which are more suitable for shorter time horizons [2].

NWP models simulate atmospheric circulation and provide weather parameters such as wind speed, cloud cover, temperature, and pressure and they have advanced significantly in recent years due to, e.g., improved understanding of atmospheric dynamics and enhanced computational capacity. Nevertheless, these models still exhibit errors due to, for instance, the uncertainty in the

initial and boundary conditions [5]. Post-processing approaches applied to the output from these models can enable to mitigate some of these issues by establishing relationships between local (e.g., solar power PV) and large-scale (e.g., cloud cover) variables to provide location-specific forecasts.

In the post-processing approaches, most of the literature available explores advanced forecast methods like machine learning, ensemble, and hybrid models to improve the power forecast, e.g., [6]. While promising, these models, are complex and need extensive tuning, making challenge to interpret and adopt them and, most of them, show only minor performance improvements. On the other hand, recent studies indicate that an optimal selection of the meteorological input parameters from NWP data can have a superior impact in the accuracy of vRES power forecasts [7].

Historically, power forecast research has predominantly focused on individual analysis of wind or solar PV power, neglecting the potential benefits of their combination in reducing the combined forecast errors. This potential can be explored in concepts such as hybrid power plants (HPPs). HPPs incorporate two or more renewable sources (and it can include storage) sharing the same point of common coupling (Pcc) [8], [9]. This concept can contribute to the fulfilment of European decarbonisation objectives, due to their multiple benefits. Some of these benefits are: i) no need to reinforce transmission grid, and ii) synergetic use of grid assets [10], [11].

The literature regarding power forecast HPPs is still limited. For instance, Lindberg et al. [8] using probabilistic forecasts examined how aggregation affects forecasting accuracy in a HPP with wind and solar technology. They found that a ratio

of 50-60% wind power, along with solar PV, is the one that enables to obtain the most accurate forecasts. [9] Using a deterministic forecast approach Couto and Estanqueiro [ref.] quantify the market value and remuneration for different HPPs considering the hybridization of existing wind power plant with solar PV. As expected, the economic metric values increased for a HPP when compared with the existing wind power plant, regardless of the level of complementarity or additional solar PV capacity added.

In this work, the benefits of wind power plant hybridisation with solar PV are assessed using probabilistic forecasts. This "new" market player is being addressed in the TradeRES project [12]. The most effective forecasting approach, namely, which meteorological parameters should be used as input is also addressed in this work. This work introduces a probabilistic power forecasting method tailored for HPPs. The methodology integrates a sequential forward feature selection algorithm, which incorporates distinct objective functions and an artificial neural network approach. Then, the probabilistic power forecasts are obtained using a quantile spline regression technique. The proposed methodology enables to determine of the optimal quantile and the selection of exogenous features (e.g., meteorological input from NWP models) that fulfil each objective function analysed in the work. The methodology is applied to two case studies in Portugal. Results are analysed considering technical (Normalized Mean Square Error – RMSE and Continuous Ranked Probability Score - CRPS) and economic (the profitability of HPP in both day-ahead and balancing markets within the Iberian electricity market) indicators.

Section 2 discusses the types of power forecast outputs. Section 3 presents the methodology while in section 4 the data, case studies and scenarios are presented. Section 5 presents and discusses the main results obtained. Finally, in section 6 some final remarks are provided.

2. Deterministic and probabilistic power forecast outputs

Initially, power forecast systems were designed to deliver deterministic information, providing an expected single value for each time step of the forecast horizon. However, deterministic forecasts lack information regarding the uncertainty, which is crucial for the TSOs and market players to make informed decisions, such as strategic bidding [13]. Recognizing the importance of characterizing uncertainty in renewable energy forecasts, various probabilistic forecasting techniques have been developed [14]. Probabilistic forecasts can offer valuable benefits, such as enhancing market players revenues and enabling adequate reserve allocation [15].

Broadly speaking, probabilistic forecasts provide upper and lower bounds of expected generation in the form of probability density or interval. This probability density or interval can be obtained using physical approaches (e.g., NWP ensembles), statistical methods, or a combination of both ensembles [16]. The NWP ensemble forecasts are computationally demanding and may have inferior performance compared to statistical methods. Power forecast

uncertainty using statistical/hybrid models can be determined based on: i) parametric distribution parameters, ii) nonparametric regression assumptions such as quantile regressions or kernel density estimators, or iii) historical analogous events [17], [18]. An discussion regarding the probabilistic forecast can be found in [16].

3 Methodology

This work extended the methodology presented by Couto and Estanqueiro [9], [19] by incorporating probabilistic information to calibrate the forecast and also include an additional objective function that taking into account the distribution of the prob. Fig. 1 illustrates a flowchart with the main steps of the proposed methodology. A detailed explanation of each step is described in [9], while in the next section a brief description is provided.

In this study, a price-taker approach was adopted meaning that individual market participants as small relative contribution to the overall market, and, therefore, they cannot influence the market prices.

Fig. 1. Flowchart illustrating the main steps for generating the power forecasts (adapted from [9]). The orange dotted line is used according to objective function chosen.

3.1 Principal Component Analysis as data dimension reduction approach

The principal component analysis (PCA), applied following a z-score normalization process for each meteorological field, enables to identify dominant spatial-temporal synoptic variability modes while eliminating poorly correlated local effects. This reduction of dimensions in the dataset is achieved by expressing a meteorological variable as a linear combination of spatial patterns and time-dependent weights. The first principal component (PC) captures the highest variance, with subsequent PCs capturing the remaining uncorrelated variance. In this study, PCA is conducted individually for each meteorological parameter, with the number of retained PCs determined to account for 90% of the total variance. The retained PCs are then ranked based on their distance correlation with the observed power. Then,

each PC iteratively feed the forward feature selection algorithm that retains only the ones that enable to fulfil the objective function.

3.2 Feature selection approach applied to NWP-based features

Feature selection (FS) methods aim to efficiently reduce data and enhance model accuracy. In this work, a wrapper technique, Sequential Forward Feature Selection (SFFS), is employed. SFFS iteratively selects meteorological features that minimize prediction errors, starting with the feature showing the highest Pearson correlation with observed power. An artificial neural network (ANN) is then utilized to obtain forecasts using different subsets of meteorological parameters. The process is repeated iteratively for all input variables, ensuring robust forecast results.

3.3 Power forecasts using artificial neural networks

ANNs, commonly used for wind and solar power forecasts, recognize patterns and make predictions based on input/output data. They consist of input, hidden, and output layers, with the number of neurons and layers influencing network performance. Training ANNs involves adjusting weights and biases to minimize differences between predicted and target outputs. The Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm is employed for training due to its efficiency in handling high-dimensional optimization tasks.

The ANN architecture used is similar to the one presented in [9]. For the initial iteration of the SFFS, where only one feature is available, the input layer of the neural network comprises two neurons. Subsequently, the number of neurons in the hidden layer is determined by taking two-thirds of the size of the input layer plus the size of the output layer, with rounding up as necessary. A sigmoid function is used as the transfer function from the input to the hidden layer, and also it is employed from the hidden to the output layer. Training of the ANN utilizes the LM algorithm and continues until one of three criteria is met: reaching the maximum iteration limit (1,000), achieving the minimum gradient ($1e-7$), or attaining a network performance, as measured by sum square of the errors, equal to the minimum threshold of 0. This methodology is implemented using the neural network toolbox from the MATLAB [20].

Based on the deterministic forecast obtained from the ANN, the probabilistic power forecasts are generated using a quantile B-spline method to regress the hourly observed power against the point power forecasts. Thus, for each hourly period t , a vector of power forecast quantiles $\hat{Q}_{t|t+k_t}^\tau$ is produced for probabilities $\tau \in (0.05, 0.10, \dots, 0.95)$.

3.4 Objective functions used in the power forecast calibration

Three distinct objective functions were employed individually to calibrate the power forecasts, with each aimed at selecting the most suitable meteorological parameters. These objectives include: i) minimizing the normalized root mean square error (equation 1), ii) minimizing the continuous ranked probability score (CRPS) [6], and iii) maximizing the total market remuneration in an electricity market setting,

considering both the day-ahead and balancing markets (equation 3). For the first and third objective functions, calculations are performed for each quantile. Consequently, in the SFFS, the quantile that minimizes or maximizes the respective objective function is considered in each iteration.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t=1}^T (\hat{P}_t - P_t)^2}{T}} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Remuneration} \\ & = \sum_{t=1}^T \hat{P}_t Price_{DAM,t} \\ & + \begin{cases} (P_t - \hat{P}_t) Price_{Up,t} & \text{for } \hat{P}_t < P_t \\ (\hat{P}_t - P_t) Price_{Down,t} & \text{for } \hat{P}_t > P_t \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In the previous equations \hat{P}_t and P_t are the hourly average power forecasted and observed, respectively. Where $Price_{DAM,t}$ represents the day-ahead market hourly prices, and $Price_{Up,t}$ and $Price_{Down,t}$ are the hourly upward and downward imbalance prices provided by the Portuguese TSO.

In the case of CRPS, the metric assesses the capability of a probabilistic forecast by considering the entire predictive cumulative distribution function. CRPS tends to favour distributions with narrower uncertainty intervals. The ideal value of this metric is zero, which means a complete alignment between the forecasted cumulative distribution function and the observed distribution. Therefore, the objective function used in this case was the minimization of the CRPS.

3.5 Assessing the power forecast performance – metrics

In this study, both technical and economic metrics are used to evaluate the performance of power forecasts enabling to obtain insights according to the different perspectives. The technical metrics used include the RMSE (Equation 1), the normalized RMSE (NRMSE), and the continuous ranked probability score (CRPS). The NRMSE is calculated by dividing the RMSE by the average observed power production of each case study and scenario. Optimal values for RMSE, NRMSE, and CRPS are all equal to zero. For the economic assessment the weighted market remuneration is used (Equation 3).

$$\text{Weighted Remuneration} = \frac{\text{Remuneration}}{\sum_{t=1}^T P_t} \quad (3)$$

To compare the different scenarios analysed, the approach followed in [21] is used for each metric, Equation 4. In this equation $Forecast_{Scenario}$ represents the results of a metric for a specific scenario, and $Forecast_{Benchmark}$ represents the results of the same metric in the benchmark scenario.

$$\varepsilon = \left(1 - \frac{Forecast_{Scenario}}{Forecast_{Benchmark}} \right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

4 Data, case studies and scenarios

This study uses data ranging from January 1, 2017, to December 31, 2019. The data sources included: a) NWP data from a NWP mesoscale model, and 2) observed data collected from wind and solar parks as well as hourly data from the electricity market (day-ahead market and the surplus or deficit from Portuguese imbalance costs) [22].

4.1 NWP forecast data

NWP models have become integral to weather forecasting, evolving significantly over time due to improved understanding of atmospheric dynamics and computational advancements. These models, categorized as global or regional/mesoscale, incorporate detailed physical parameterizations to provide more accurate forecasts. This study used data from the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) mesoscale model with a 12-kilometre grid resolution provided by MeteoGalia [23]. The selected parameters used in this work are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1 – Meteorological-based parameters used in this work. Adapted from [9]. The parameters in italic are computed based on NWP outcomes.

Information obtained	Meteorological Parameter	Units
Single level	Atmospheric visibility	m
	Cloud area fraction in high atmosphere layer	[0 1]
	Cloud area fraction in medium atmosphere layer	[0 1]
	Cloud area fraction in low atmosphere layer	[0 1]
	Cloud cover at low and medium layers	[0 1]
	Convective available potential energy	J kg ⁻¹
	Convective inhibition	J kg ⁻¹
	Precipitation convective	kg m ⁻²
	Precipitation	kg m ⁻²
	Humidity relative at 2 meters	[0 1]
	Mean sea level pressure	Pa
	Planetary boundary layer height	m
	Surface downwelling longwave flux	W m ⁻²
	Surface downwelling shortwave flux	W m ⁻²
	Surface downward latent heat flux	W m ⁻²
	Surface downward sensible heat flux	W m ⁻²
	Surface wind speed gust	m/s
	Sea surface temperature	K
	<i>Mean sea level pressure gradient [9]</i>	Pa m ⁻¹
	<i>Wind shear [9]</i>	Dimensionless
<i>Wind power density at sigma levels 0.986</i>	W m ⁻²	
<i>Vertical temperature variation</i>	K	
Multiple level	Air temperature at 500, 850, and 2 meters	K
	Geopotential height at 500, 850 and sigma level 0.986	m
	U-wind component at sigma levels 0.994 and 0.986, and 10 meters	m s ⁻¹
	V-wind component at sigma levels 0.994 and 0.986, and 10 meters	m s ⁻¹
	Wind speed at sigma levels 0.994, 0.986 and 10 meters	m s ⁻¹

4.2 Wind and hybrid power plants data

The existing wind parks under analysis in this work have an equal nominal capacity of 20 MW. Due to the absence of publicly available data for hybrid wind and solar PV parks, existing small-scale solar PV power plants near wind parks were utilized as an alternative aiming to mimic the behaviour of HPP sharing the same Pcc. To enhance the impact of solar PV technology within the HPP, the observed data ($SolarPV_t$) was upscaled considering the installed ($SolarCapacity$) and a 10 MW peak capacity. Equation 5 was employed to compute hourly solar production ($SolarPV_{10MWp,t}$) within each HPP, taking into account the peak capacity of the solar PV power plant and existing hourly production.

$$SolarPV_{10MWp,t} = \frac{10}{SolarCapacity} SolarPV_t \quad (5)$$

The $SolarCapacity$ is 0.14 MW in case study 1 (hereafter designated as HPP1) and 2.00 MW in HPP2 case study.

4.3 Case studies characterization

For confidentiality reasons, the exact locations or coordinates of the HPPs cannot be indicated. However, as presented in [9], HPP1 is situated in the inner regions of the north of Portugal being the Pearson correlation coefficient [11] between wind and solar PV generation negative at both hourly and daily temporal scales. Therefore, this HPP exhibits complementarity between wind and solar PV generation in these two temporal scales. The HPP2, located in southern region of Portugal presented positive correlation values. Thus, for this case study, there is similarity in the wind and solar PV generation.

4.4 Power forecast scenarios

This section presents the scenarios and the results from the application of the methodology to the two HPPs. Table 2 summarizes the scenarios analysed in this study and their specifications.

Table 2. Characterization of the scenarios analysed.

Type of power plant	Scenario	Probabilistic forecast?	Obj. function in the SFFS algorithm		
			Min. RMSE	Min. CRPS	Max. Remuneration
Wind	Wind_Det.	No	X		
	Wind_Prob.	Yes	X		
Hybrid (wind and solar PV)	Hybrid_RMSE	Yes	X		
	Hybrid_CRPS	Yes		X	
	Hybrid_MARKET	Yes			X

In addition, the following specifications for the each scenario conducted were considered:

- Hybridization of wind power plant with 10 MW.
- The maximum injection capacity allowed was 20 MW. If the sum of generation from wind and solar power exceeds 20 MW for any given hour, the combined power value is capped at 20 MW.
- The forecast methodology was calibrated using data from January 1, 2017, to June 30, 2019.
- The validation dataset comprises data from July 1, 2019, to December 31, 2019.

The benchmark for this study is the forecast for existing wind power plants, utilizing *Wind_Prob.* scenario, *i.e.*, the use of minimization of RMSE as objective function in the SFFS algorithm.

5 Power forecast results

5.1. The impact of the SFFS algorithm in the selection of the most relevant features

Fig. 2 presents the different iterations of the SFFS during the optimization process to identify the most relevant meteorological features in the case of HPP2. The values were normalized considering the RMSE value with only one feature.

Fig. 2. RMSE improvement during the iterations of the SFFS algorithm for two scenarios in the case of HPP2.

From the previous figure, it is possible to understand that the selection of the different objective functions has an impact on the features selected, and, consequently, on the results obtained. In both cases, the highest improvements are observed in the first features introduced in the SFFS despite the number of features used are slightly different. After testing the 10 features with the highest correlation with the observed power, the improvements identified reached nearly 25% compared with the use of only one feature. In the case of *Hybrid_RMSE* the highest improvement identified was 35.27% by selecting 19 meteorological features. The feature introduced in 58th place (cloud fraction at lower-level parameter) was the last one to enable an improvement in the optimization process. In the case of *Hybrid_MARKET* scenario, the improvement was only 33.46% compared with the initial value.

The benefits of using the SFFS algorithm are underlined in Fig. 3. This figure presents the RMSE improvement results after obtaining 5, 10 e all features that enable to accomplish with the different objective functions.

Fig. 3. RMSE improvements for the different scenarios considering 5, 10 and all meteorological features identified with the SFFS.

From Fig. 3 it can be observed that as the number of features used increases the error tends to reduce significantly. The improvements are particularly relevant for hybrid power plants that benefit from a careful selection of the most relevant parameters. The meteorological parameters selected in the different scenarios vary slightly including in the number of the principal components. The predominant meteorological parameters identified in the HPP scenarios were: wind speed at different levels of the atmosphere, wind gust, components of meridional and longitudinal of wind speed, planetary boundary layer height, Surface downward sensible heat flux, Surface downward latent heat flux. Other parameters computed based on the outputs from the NWP model were also identified by the SFFS algorithm, namely, wind power density, mean sea level gradient pressure, and wind shear, which are not commonly used in the power forecast systems.

5.2. Assessment of the power forecasts performance

Table 3 and Table 4 present the results of the different metrics for the two case studies under analysis in this work. In the following tables, for the case of RMSE and CRPS a negative value represents an improvement compared with the benchmark.

Table 3. Results of the evaluation metrics for the different scenarios comparing with the *Wind_Prob* scenario – HPP1.

Scenario	RMSE	CRPS	Weighted Remuneration
<i>Wind_Det</i>	2.5	-	-0.2
<i>Hybrid_RMSE</i>	1.0	-1.5	10.7
<i>Hybrid_CRPS</i>	2.9	-1.9	10.7
<i>Hybrid_MARKET</i>	3.7	-1.7	10.8

Table 4. Results of the evaluation metrics for the different scenarios comparing with the *Wind_Prob* scenario – HPP2.

Scenario	RMSE	CRPS	Weighted Remuneration
<i>Wind_Det</i>	2.5	-	-0.1
<i>Hybrid_RMSE</i>	-1.3	-3.6	2.6
<i>Hybrid_CRPS</i>	-1.2	-3.9	2.6
<i>Hybrid_MARKET</i>	-1.2	-2.7	2.7

Results from previous tables highlight the benefit of using probabilistic forecasts. Since the training and validation datasets are distinct, the corrections introduced by probabilistic forecasts can help to improve the performance of the forecast. Although the differences are not significant, the results also demonstrate dependence on the objective function. Therefore, in cases where, *e.g.*, the goal is to maximize the remuneration, the SFFS algorithm should be

optimized with this objective function to identify the most relevant meteorological parameters.

It is possible to observe that, even with a 10 MW increase in the total capacity of the existing wind power plant, the increase in error in a hybridization scenario compared to the existing wind plant is not meaningful (in the case of HPP1). In fact, for the HPP2 is possible to observe a reduction in the RMSE values in the case of hybridization of existing wind power plant. When employing the CRPS objective function, which considers the probability distribution of the forecasts, hybridization could potentially decrease errors in this metric across all scenarios. This outcome can be explained by a more accurate characterization of the probability distribution, achieved in the combined (wind and solar PV) time series with less variability and extreme values, when compared to the time series of the existing wind power plant.

Due to the reduced remuneration of HPP1 and the wind and solar PV generation complementarity level, a more significant increase (greater than 10%) can be observed in this plant. In the case of HPP2, hybridization is also beneficial. However, the remuneration increment values are lower (around 3%).

Finally, the findings indicate no significant differences in the results when a metric incorporating information from all quantiles (CRPS) is used compared with deterministic-based metrics (e.g., RMSE) using the quantile that maximize or minimize an objective function.

Fig. 4 presents the NRMSE for HPP2, after identifying all the meteorological features that enable accomplishing with the different objective functions.

Fig. 4. NRMSE for the different quantiles and scenarios in HPP2. The symbol "x" represents the minimum value for the different scenarios.

Fig. 4 illustrates the advantage of using probabilistic forecasts. As expected, the lowest error is observed in the *Hybrid_RMSE* scenario that aims to minimizing RMSE. This minimum value is identified at the 50th percentile. In contrast, for the other scenarios, the lowest RMSE error is identified at the 55th percentile, indicating that maximizing remuneration or minimizing CRPS may result in forecasts with higher RMSE values. These findings highlight the complex relationship between error minimization and market remuneration maximization. Consequently, the forecast approach should always be calibrated according to the objectives of each user.

5.3. Obtaining added value from probabilistic forecasts for new market products

As the share of wind and solar PV increases in the market, these types of power plants will need to be active players in the market. Therefore, these players should be capable of strategically participate in the different market products such as day-ahead, intra-day and ancillary services. Nevertheless, the participation in ancillary services will require the capability of these technologies to ensure that the bid capacity is available at a specific time enabling to replace other conventional technologies.

To identify the added value of hybridization of existing wind power plants, Fig. 5 shows the percentage of time in which the observed production is above a certain percentile and the respective average hourly power that would be available in these periods, for HPP2.

Fig. 5. Percentage of time with the observed power above the quantile forecast and respective average power for HPP2.

In Fig. 5 is possible to verify that the percentage of time with observed power above the 5% and 10% quantiles is relatively similar for the different scenarios, especially when considering the objective function of minimizing the error. However, on average, the power available is substantially higher in the case of the HPPs when compared with the wind power plant case. The increase in the capacity available is above 1 MW in both quantiles. This capacity could be used, with a high degree of confidence, to provide system services currently provided by other types of technologies representing an additional revenue stream.

6 Final remarks

This work addressed the probabilistic power forecasts for hybrid power plants. This market player is being addressed in the TradeRES project as a way to increase the technical and economic value of existing power plants.

Results underline the benefit of using probabilistic power forecast approaches with the identification of the quantile that maximizes or minimizes the different objective functions used. As expected, the economic metric values increased for a HPP, when compared with the existing wind power plant, regardless of the level of complementarity of the technologies that compose the HPP. The simulations showed that weighted remuneration increases nearly 3% in HPP2 and 10% in HPP1, compared with the forecasts for existing wind power

plants - benchmark scenario. Despite a 10 MW capacity increase, the forecast errors do not increase proportionally. Indeed, there is a slight reduction in the errors observed for the HPP2 compared to the benchmark scenario.

Results indicate that an appropriate selection and the use of objective functions are essential to calibrate the forecasting methodology according to user needs, particularly in the context of HPP, where different technologies are involved.

Hybridizing existing wind power plants can significantly contribute to the ongoing energy transition by offering several advantages such as increasing the capacity factor of the power plants. Moreover, this type of power plant can also be important within a market environment since it can give a more comfortable condition to support the diversification of the revenue streams in response to market conditions, particularly in the context of nearly 100% renewable power systems.

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